

The Role of Additives in Processed Food, Shelf Life and Health

*Shreyash Mithare¹, Sujal Ambewadi¹, G Vijaya Kumar² and Trilok Chandran²

1 Department of Electronics and Communication, RV College of Engineering, Mysore Road, Bangalore – 59

2 Department of Biotechnology, RV College of Engineering, Mysore Road, Bangalore – 59

Abstract

Food is consumed in a solid, semi solid and liquid form so that humans ingest to receive nutritional advantages. Food additives, which are organic chemicals used in minute quantities during food processing and manufacture, are essential for maintaining and prolonging the shelf life of processed foods and also to prevent the growth of microorganisms. Generally, the preservatives can be categorized in to Chemical and Natural preservatives. Edible oils, sugar, salt, and honey etc., come under natural preservatives, whereas benzoates, sorbates, nitrites, nitrates sulphites, glutamates et., comes under chemical preservatives. Food preservation is essential for extending the shelf life and improving processed food quality. This review research paper aims to offer a comprehensive examination of the state of knowledge on role of additives in preservation of food.

Keywords: Additives, Shelf life, Preservatives, Health, Processed food.

Introduction

Food is a material that gives vital nutrients for survival and functioning of the eco system. Food is derived from plants and animals which has essential elements including vitamins, proteins, lipids, and carbohydrates. Food additives are frequently added in little amounts to enhance the flavors, texture or appearance of their products during production or processing of the food.

Acceptable daily intakes (ADIs) are safe limits within which these chemicals must be used since exceeding the ADI can put the consumers at danger. Additives (Natural and artificial) are added to maintain the food consistent, impart (Carmen) color to food, sweeten (aspheric acid) the food. Preservatives are only added to keep food fresher, longer, and prevention from the growth of bacteria, mold, and yeast. For food to remain fresh and to retain its quality, consistency, and flavors, additives and preservatives must be used. The study of food chemistry looks at the chemical reactions and interactions that occur between food's biological and non-biological components. Products that are biological include milk, pork, chicken, and beer. As processed foods gained popularity in the latter half of the 20th century, the usage of both natural and artificial additives is gaining importance.

Artificial substances are commonly found in products like coffee creamer and candy, and studies have shown that many of these additives may be harmful to health. In the present days, lot of people choose ready to cook meals, which frequently have chemicals and preservatives added to them to improve flavor and preserve freshness.

Sodium nitrate, BHA, monosodium glutamate, and sodium benzoate are common preservatives and additives. Artificial colors like Red (erythrosine and amaranth) and yellow-orange (annatto-bixine) are also commonly used.

Food and its classification [2,9].

Agricultural activities such as farming, fishing, and hunting were the means by which people obtained food in the past. However, the food business, which is controlled by multinational corporations and uses intensive farming and industrial agricultural techniques, now provides the majority of the food.

Classifications of food additives

Food additives can be divided into four general categories; Nutritional Additives, processing additives, preservatives and sensory agents.

1.Nutritional Additives: They are used as a fortification or supplements to make up for nutrients that are lost during the manufacturing process. The first food fortification occurred in 1924 when iodine was added to table salt to stop goiter. Vitamins are frequently added to foods to boost their nutritional value. Cereals, pasta, baked goods, and wheat all have vitamin B, whereas fruit drinks, cereals, and dairy products all include vitamin C. Contrarily, dairy and cereal items usually contain vitamins A and D.

2.Processing agents: Many agents listed in the table 1, are added to food during processing in order to maintain the consistency of the product.

Table 1.0: List of the processing agents

Function	Chemical agent found	Product obtained
Anticaking	Sodium aluminosilicate	Salt
Bleaching	Benzoyl peroxide	Flour
Chelating	Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA)	Dressings, sauces and dried bananas
Emulsifiers	Lecithin	Ice cream, bakery
Humectants	Glycerol	Soft candies and chewing gum
pH Control	Citric acid and lactic acid	Cheese, jams and jellies
Stabilizers and thickeners	Pectin, Gelatin, gums	Dressings, jams and jellies, puddings

3.Preservatives

They are divided into two groups: Antioxidants and Antimicrobials.

Antioxidants are compounds that inhibit oxidation, a chemical reaction that can produce free radicals. Autoxidation leads to degradation of organic compounds, including living matter. These are substances that are added to fats, and products containing fat in order to slow down oxidation and guard against specific kinds of cellular damage.

A good antioxidant shouldn't give the bad tastes, smells, or colors for the food. It ought to be safe to eat, effective at low doses, and fat-soluble. Butylated hydroxyanisole (BHA), butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT), and tertiary butyl hydroquinone (TBHQ), which are all phenolic chemicals, are common antioxidants found in food (Dalton, 2002). Moreover, thiodipropionic acid and Dilauryl thiodipropionate are used as dietary antioxidants. Because it is more expensive than synthetic antioxidants, tocopherol—a naturally occurring antioxidant that serves as a biological shield in plant and animal tissues is not frequently added to food [15]. Some of the antioxidants and their mode of action is presented in Table 2.0.

Table 2.0: List of antioxidants and their mode of action

Chemical agents	Mode of action
Ascorbic acid	Oxygen scavenger
Butylated hydroxyanisole	Free radical scavenger
Citric acid	Enzyme inhibitor
Sulfites	Enzyme inhibitor
Tocopherols	Free radical scavenger

Antimicrobial agents: These are used to stop growth of bacteria from causing food to deteriorate. Examples of common ingredients in products like baked goods, salad dressings, cheese, and pickled foods are vinegar, salt, calcium propionate, and sorbic acid [15]. Few of the chemicals used for antimicrobial functions in food processing is listed in table 3.0.

Table 3.0: List of antioxidants and their mode of action

Chemical agents	Mode of action
Acetic acid	Destroy cell membrane function such as yeasts, bacteria and molds
Benzoic acid	Destroy cell membrane and inhibits enzyme such as molds, bacteria and yeasts
Nitrates and nitrites	Inhibit enzymes and destroy cell membrane function
Sulfites and sulfur dioxide	Inhibit enzymes and forms addition compounds such as yeasts and bacteria
Sorbic acid	Inhibit bacterial spore germination such as yeasts, bacteria and molds

4.Sensory Agents: These include colorants, flavorants, and sweeteners.

Coloring agents: These substances are used to enhance the color of food. Coloring agents, including stabilizers and color retention agents, are added during preparation to make food more visually appealing. Color is a key sensory characteristic of food [14].

These are further classified as natural and synthetic colorants

Natural Colorants: These are derived from plants and animals; Annatto is extracted from orange pulp and used to color butter and cheese, Carotene extracted from carrots, turmeric, a spice, used to add shade to curries, meat merchandise, and salad dressings. Cochineal, however, is derived from the woman insect (*Coccus cacti*). [16]

Artificial coloring agents: These colorants come in powder, paste, or granule form and are soluble in water. Synthetic colorants encompass substances such as tartrazine and erythrosine.

Flavors and flavor enhancers: Food flavor can be improved by using flavor enhancers. Initially back to the history in Asia, where it was customary to add sea weed to soup stocks to enhance the flavor.

The discovery that the amino acid L-glutamate has flavor enhancing qualities in seaweed led to the creation of monosodium glutamate (MSG), the first flavor enhancer to be used commercially is *L-glutamate* having a umami taste is a complex flavor experience. It's normal practice to add MSG to processed meals like sauces and soups. Herbs and spices are examples of natural flavor additives; ethyl butyrate, which is used to give food a pineapple flavor, is an example of a synthetic flavoring [14].

Sweeteners: Foods are flavored with the use of sweeteners. They are divided into varieties that are nutritious and those that are not. Sweeteners that are high in calories and rich in carbohydrates provide energy, corn syrup, fructose, glucose, and sucrose are a few examples. On the other hand, non-nutritive sweeteners, which include aspartame and saccharin, are low in calories. Chewing gum and soft drinks are major sources of saccharin, whereas dairy products, low flavored milk, and sodas are common sources of aspartame [14].

Bleaching agents: Foods like cheese and wheat flour are made whiter by using peroxides, which are molecules of oxygen atoms joined together to improve the color of flour, they are added either during or after milling. Flour naturally contains xanthophylls and carotene as colors. To enhance baking quality, post milling chemicals such potassium bromate and chlorine dioxide are employed, along with benzoyl peroxide, which whitens flour [15].

Emulsifiers: Emulsifiers are used to guarantee that one liquid, like oil in water, is distributed evenly within another and to stop fats from clumping together. They are frequently discovered in shortenings, salad dressings, dairy, and baked goods. One example of an emulsifier content in peanut butter is about 10%. Emulsifiers include things like butter, which is an emulsion of water and fat, milk, which is an emulsion of fat and water, and lecithin from egg yolks. [6]

Preservatives: These synthetic additions are used to control spoiling brought on by chemical alterations, like the formation of mold. Microbial deterioration causes the loss of about one-fifth of the food produced worldwide. The two primary categories of food preservatives are antibacterial agents and antioxidants. Food oxidation is stopped by antioxidants such citric acid, ascorbic acid, and butylated hydroxyanisole. Spoilage microorganism development is inhibited by antimicrobial drugs such as sorbic acid, benzoic acid, and acetic acid [3,4].

Agents for adjusting pH: These chemicals are used to modulate food pH, which affects cooking proper- ties, flavor, and texture. They aid in controlling the food items' acidity and alkalinity. Products like cheese, jams, and jellies frequently contain chemical ingredients like lactic acid and citric acid [3,4].

Supplemental nutrients: Supplemental nutrients are given to food in order to make up for any nutritional value that might be lost via processing or storage. Foods can lose some of their nutrients during preparation, thus additives are employed to make up for this; Brown colored vitamin and mineral rich portion of the grain is removed during the milling process of wheat to make white flour. Thiamine, nicotinic acid, calcium, and iron are added to the flour to make up for this loss. Citrus fruits that have been canned also receive an addition of vitamin C to replenish the vitamin lost during processing [3,4].

Bulking Agents: Bulking agents are used to increase the volume or weight of food without altering its nutritional value. These agents add bulk to food products, such as bakery items, confectioneries, sauces, soups, and processed

meats. Examples of bulking agents include soluble fibers like guar gum and starch. They help enhance the bulk of foods while maintaining their nutritional content [3,4].

Additional additives: Renin is used to produce cheese and curd, papain is used to tenderize meat, and pectinase is used to clear drinks. Fruits and vegetables retain their freshness thanks to firming chemicals like aluminum sulphates and calcium salts. Liquid nitrogen and other freezing chemicals are used to quickly chill food. To lessen haziness, clarifying chemicals including bentonite, gelatin, and synthetic resins are used. Enzymes help food products undergo modifications that are desired. Flavors, pigments, and other substances are dissolved using solvents like glycerin and alcohol. Instant food packaging uses packing gases, such as inert gases like neon and helium, to stop oxidation and other changes [3,4].

E Numbering:

E-numbers, with "E" standing for "Europe," are codes assigned to food additives that occur naturally in many foods, such as vitamin C. These unique numbers help manage and inform consumers about the nature of these additives, with each additive receiving a specific E-number for approval within Europe. For instance, Additive 103 (alkane) is not approved in Europe and thus lacks an E-number, though it has been permitted in Australia and New Zealand since 1987. Australia also has a system for labeling food additives, using numbers similar to the European system but without the 'E' prefix. Some examples of E-numbers for dietary supplements include Tartrazine (E102), Quinoline Yellow (E104), Carmoisine (E122), and Amaranth (E123) [12]. Table 4 & 5 presents the E numbers for the various food additives and E Numbers given for some of the additives with examples

Table 4.0: range of E-Numbers given for the various food additive

Uses	E Numbers
Food colours	E100 – 199
Preservatives	E200 – 299
Antioxidants	E300 – 399
Emulsifiers and stabilizers	E400 – 499
Anticaking agents	E500 – 599
Flavour enhancers	E600 – 699
Sweeteners	E900 – 999

Table 5.0: List of the additives with their E number

Number	Name	Description	Examples
E100	Curcumin	Naturally occurring orange and yellow colour that is extracted from spice turmeric	Used in pastries, sauces and soups
E101	Riboflavin	Naturally occurring B group vitamin that is obtained from yeast	Added to processed cheese as yellow and orange colour
E102	Tartrazine	Used as yellow or orange colour	Found in cakes, biscuits, meat products and sauces
E120	Cochineal	It is a natural red colour that is obtained from egg yolk	Red colour used in foods.
E123	Amaranth	It is a synthetic coal tar dye and is red in colour	Used in gravy, blackcurrant drinks
E127	Erythrosine	It is a synthetic coal tar dye and is red in colour and rich in mineral iodine.	Used in tinned strawberries and certain flavours of chips and potato-based snacks.
E140	Chlorophyll	It is a naturally occurring green pigment that is found in leaves and stems of plants.	Used in green vegetables in order to enhance colour.
E150	Caramel	Used as brown colour and flavouring agent that is made from burning of sugar by heat.	It is used in soft drinks, gravy, cakes, biscuits and beef products.

E160	Carotenoids	It is a plant pigment that is derived from carrots, oranges and rosehip. It is a plant pigment that is derived from carrots, oranges and rosehip.	Helps to provide a range of colours from yellow to red.
E162	Betainin (beetroot red)	It is a naturally occurring red or purple colour in beetroot.	Added to oxtail soup.
E163	Anthocyanins	These are plant pigments that have colours ranging from red to blue.	They are present in red cabbage and grapes.
E172	Iron oxide	They are added to fortify food	Used in flour and cereals
E200	Sorbic acid	These are generally manufactured synthetically for use as a food preservative.	Used in soft drinks, pizza and cakes
E210	Benzoic acid	Occurs in cherry bark, raspberries and tea.	They act as a preservative and anti-oxidant in fruit products, salad dressings and soft drinks.
E260	Acetic acid	It is a natural component of vinegar that is generally manufactured from wood and is used as preservative and acid.	It is used in pickles and chutneys.
E270	Lactic acid	It is produced by fermentation of lactose. Occurs in yogurt and soured milk that acts as a preservative.	Used in cakes, biscuits and salad dressings.
E306	Tocopherols (vitamin E)	They are obtained from wheat germ, cotton seed, maize and green leaves and is used as antioxidant and nutrient.	Added in fats and oils.
E330	Citric acid	Occurs in citrus fruits and can be prepared from fermentation of molasses. Used as an antioxidant, preservative and flour improver.	They are added in pickles, dairy and baked products.
E334	Tartaric acid	These are natural products of wine making that are used as acid regulator.	They are added to baking powder.
E412	Guar Gum	Obtained from seed gum from a tree of pea family and is used as thickener and stabilizer.	They are added to sauces, soups and ice cream.
E415	Xanthan Gum	These are made from fermentation of carbohydrates by bacteria and is used as emulsifiers, thickeners and stabilizers.	Used in ice cream and bottled sauces.

Safety evaluation of food additives

Under food additives, two categories of ingredients are free from regulation. Modification:

Group 1: Previously authorized compounds that, before the 1958 amendment, the FDA or USDA had found safe to use in food. Examples are sodium and potassium nitrates.

Group 2: This includes GRAS (Generally Recognized as Safe). Substances approved by experts as safe based on published scientific evidence. Examples- Salt, sugar and MSG (Monosodium Glutamate).

In 1969, President Nixon instructed the FDA to review the safety features of all GRAS items on the basis of current scientific research. In 1972 a committee from the Federation of American societies for experimental biology reviewed the safety of all GRAS items on the basis of published and other available information. The committee placed all evaluated substances in five categories:

Category 1: All of the additives with reaffirmed GRAS status are included in it. This indicates that there is no proof of hazardous risks for the substance in issue in the information that is currently accessible. Typically, these products are utilized in compliance with GMP.

Category 2: It comprises drugs for which the GRAS classification has been upheld at the present usage level. This indicates that there is no proof of hazardous risks at the level of practice and present use in the information that is currently available.

Category 3: It contains those substances whose safety is reaffirmed at the level of current use and practice.

Category 4: It contains those substances whose information is incomplete to “reaffirm safety”. This means the level of toxicity has been reported, yet the level and manner of current use the information is insufficient to determine the impact on public health.

Category 5: Those that do not have biological studies available to judge their safety [12].

Recommendations

In order to improve the current condition, the following recommendations are suggested

1. The food additives which are not essential should be banned.
2. Various regulatory concern should make sure that food additives that are Generally Recognized as Safe (GRAS) should be added to foods.
3. All foods consisting of additives with carcinogenic, mutagenic and teratogenic properties should be clearly labeled with appropriate warning.
4. All food additives should be prohibited from foods that are consumed by infants and young children.
5. All food Additives which are not generally recognized as safe (GRAS) should not increase the acceptable daily Intakes (ADIs).
6. All the food items that have very less or no nutritional value should be removed from all promotions.
7. Regulatory agencies must ensure that Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP) are followed by various food and processing industries.
8. The government should also introduce free nutritious school meals, preferably using natural foods, which will be available to all school children to discourage them from patronizing these colorant food additives [13].

Conclusion

This research paper has surveyed the numerous effects of food preservatives and additives on man's life. They have been used for many years and are used to preserve foods, flavor, thicken, blend and have played an important role in maintaining the nutritional values. Additives help to maintain the availability of healthy, tasty and affordable food that meets the needs of consumers from season to season and also helps to protect food from getting spoiled by microorganisms. Food additives play an important role in food processing industries but the adverse effects caused by them remain a problem. Artificial food additives respond to the cellular portion of the body leading to various food effects. If we want to use food additives, they should be natural ones that have minimum effect and should be Generally Recognized as Safe (GRAS). For those that are not generally recognized as safe, the acceptable daily intakes (ADIs) should be reduced. In order to reduce the risk of health problems due to various food preservatives and additives, we must avoid that type of food which contain these additives and preservatives. Before buying the canned food items its ingredients and composition should be checked. Always try to buy that type of product which are organic and free from synthetic additives. Before buying any food product, we should check regulatory bodies of food.

Acknowledgement: We acknowledge RVCE for providing opportunity for kind support to carrying out the present work.

References

1. Shaziakhanummirza, *et al.*, To study the harmful effects of food preservatives on human health. 2017;2:610-616
2. Inetanbor JE, Juliet Yukubu., and EC Stephen. (2015). Effects of food additives and preservatives on man. *Asian Journal of science and technology*. 6, 2, 1118-1135.
3. Abdulmumeen HA., Risikat AN., and Sururah AR. (2012). Food: Its preservatives, additives and applications. *Int. J Chem. Biochem. Sci*, 1, 36 – 47.
4. Tuormaa TE. (1994). The additives effects of food additives on health: A review of the literature with special emphasis on childhood hyperactivity. *J Orthomol. Med*. 9, 4, 225 – 243.
5. Alpana Deshpande., and Bhagyashree Deshpande. (2017). Food additives and preservation. *Indian J Sci. Res*. 13, 2, 219 – 225.
6. Mall Neelam and Sunita Mishra. (2018). Effects of Food Additives and Preservatives on Processed Food. *Asian Journal of science and technology*. 7, 2, 30 – 32.
7. Sharma S. (2015). Food preservatives and their harmful effects. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*. 4(5), 1 – 2.
8. Boca FL., and Smoley CK. (1993). U.S. Food and Drug Administration. Everything Added to Food in the United States. CRC Press, Inc., New York; 171.
9. Federal Food., Drug, and Cosmetic Act. Section 409(b)(2). (1958). U.S. Government Printing Office, Washington.

8. Feng F., Zhao Y., Yong W., Sun L., Jiang G., and Chu X. (2011). Highly sensitive and accurate screening of 40 dyes in soft drinks by liquid chromatography-electrospray tandem mass spectrometry. *J. Chromatogr. B Anal. Technol. Biomed. Life Sci.* 879, 1813-1818.
9. Floch MH., and Annatto. (2009). Diet, and the irritable bowel syndrome. *J clin. Gastroenterol.* 43(1), 905 – 906.
10. Kriti Thakur., Dipali Singh., and Reshu Rajput. (2022). Effects of food additives and preservatives and shelf life of the processed foods. 3(2), 11 – 22.
11. Food and Drug Act of Section. (1906). 402(a)(1).
12. Khanavi M., Hajimahmoodi M., Ranjbar AM., Oveisi MR., Ardekani MRS., Mogaddam G. (2012). 13. Development of a green chromatographic method for simultaneous determination of food colorants. *Food Anal. Methods.* 5, 408 – 415.
14. Hirose M., Fukushima S., Tsuda H., Shirai T., and Tatematsu M. (1986). Studies on antioxidants: Their carcinogenic and modifying effects on chemical carcinogenesis. *Food and Chemical Toxicology.* 24(10-11), 1071 – 1082.
15. FDA. Toxicological principles for the safety assessment of direct food additives and color additives used in food (draft), Redbook II. (1983). U.S. Food and Drug Administration, Center for Food Safety and Applied Nutrition.